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MODERATING EFFECT OF BOARD INDEPENDENCE ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN AUDIT COMMITTEE ATTRIBUTES AND FINANCIAL REPORTING QUALITY AMONG LISTED FINANCIAL SERVICES FIRMS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study evaluates the influence of audit committee attributes on FRQ of financial services firms in Nigeria, with board independence as a moderating factor. The study used a longitudinal research design and panel regression analysis of eight firms from 2019 to 2024. The results show that audit committee independence and meeting frequency have significant negative effects on FRQ. This implies that these mechanisms may be largely symbolic. Similarly, audit committee shareholding has a significant negative influence on FRQ. This implies that having shares may compromise audit committee independence and create conflicts of interest. On the other hand, audit committee financial expertise and size do not have significant influence on FRQ. The moderating role of board independence shows mixed results. While it moderates positively between audit committee independence and FRQ, as predicted by agency theory, it does not have a significant moderating role for other attributes. Although it moderates the negative influence of audit committee meetings, it is still not significant. The study concludes that formal structures of corporate governance do not guarantee FRQ. The study recommends stricter audit committee independence, shareholding restrictions, competence, director appointment procedures, and stricter regulation.

Keywords: Audit Committee Attributes, Board Independence, Financial Reporting Quality, Financial Services Firms and Agency Theory .

Paper type: Research paper

Introduction

Financial Reporting Quality (FRQ) is essential for an efficient capital market and for sound economic decision-making. FRQ offers users accurate, relevant, and reliable information for assessment of firms' performance and position (Shakespeare, 2020). Enhanced FRQ improves transparency, consistency, and neutrality. However, corporate scandals and failures continue to remind us of the adverse effects of low FRQ and poor corporate governance. Worldwide, the Enron scandal has shown how corporate accounting manipulation and corporate governance failure can damage trust and confidence in corporate financial reporting (Daferighe & George, 2020).

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In Nigeria, similar concerns arise from recent corporate governance failure at Union Bank Plc, Keystone Bank Plc, and Polaris Bank Plc, where boards and management were dissolved for earnings management and non-compliance with regulations. This shows how fragile FRQ is for financial services firms (Reuters, 2024).

Corporate Governance Mechanism, specifically Audit Committees (ACs), plays an important role in ensuring FRQ. The audit committee, being an essential sub-committee of the board of directors, has the mandate of overseeing the process of financial reporting, appointing and liaising with statutory audit firms, and scrutinizing both external and internal audit reports (Abdulrahman, 2020). The watchdog of corporate financial credibility, audit committee has an essential role to play in ensuring that financial reports reflect economic reality (Babalola et al., 2025; Endrawes et al., 2020). In the past, lack of specialized corporate oversight committees led to some of the worst corporate failures. This led to reforms from the Oxley Act of 2002” (Toms, 2019; McLaughlin, 2021). In Nigeria, audit committees received statutory backing through “Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA) 1990, as amended in 2020.” Several audit committee attributes were identified by prior literature as being significant in improving the FRQ, such as independence, finance expertise, size, meeting frequency, and shareholding (Ayinla et al., 2022; Kantudu & Alhassan, 2022). Independence is highlighted as one attribute that is essential in improving the FRQ since it reduces managerial influence, agency costs, and insider opportunism, thereby improving the credibility of financial statements (Al Jahwari, 2021; Mardessi, 2021). The regulatory framework has also mandated financial literacy as well as ensuring that at least one finance expert is on the audit committee to improve members’ ability to understand complex accounting issues, manage audit risks, as well as resolve conflicts between auditors and management (Abiola & Arowolo, 2020; Mardessi, 2022). These attributes are combined to improve the FRQ through a competent audit committee.

Nonetheless, the effectiveness of the committee also relies on the size of the audit committee, as well as the meeting frequencies, which are contentious in nature. The size of the audit committee, as well as the meeting frequencies, determines the effectiveness of the committee in the organization. An adequate size of the committee would be beneficial in terms of the diversity of the members, but the committee would be too large or too small if it had an increased or decreased size, respectively, becoming less efficient or having less skill (Okeke, 2021; Komal et al., 2022). In the Nigerian environment, the size of the committee would be comprised of five members as per the CAMA 2020, and the meetings would be held quarterly as per the “Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance” (NCCG, 2018). However, the effectiveness of the committee in terms of the meeting frequencies would be less, as the meeting frequencies may be symbolic in nature (Almasria, 2022; Mardessi, 2022). Likewise, having audit committee members with shareholding interests may align their interests with those of shareholders, thereby reducing agency problems. However, in environments with ownership concentration and insider dominance, having audit committee members with shareholding interests may also threaten independence (Smith & Adewale, 2021; McLaughlin et al., 2021).

In Nigeria’s financial services sector, corporate governance failure has been related to earnings management, given the stringent regulatory environment that forces managers to engage in earnings smoothing in pursuance of regulatory and market demands (El Diri et al., 2020; Ibrahim et al., 2019). Earnings management, in the form of discretionary accruals via loan loss provisions, has been empirical evidence in Nigeria, characterized by poor audit independence and poor expertise in finance held by the audit committee (Madad et al., 2024; Kalembe et al., 2024). Despite regulatory interventions, concerns remain regarding the effectiveness of the AC in FRQ, given the poor independence and expertise in finance held by the audit committee (Aginam & Obi-Nwosu, 2024; Al-Dubai, 2023). Prior studies revealed an inconsistent relationship between AC attributes and FRQ, with studies revealing positive, negative, or insignificant effects (Hassan et al., 2020; Ogunsola, 2024; Liyayi et al., 2023). Against this background, therefore, there has been a call by various researchers to incorporate moderating variables to improve the understanding of the inconsistent findings reported by various researchers. Using the agency theory that suggests that independent boards promote oversight and reduce managerial opportunism (Vitolla et al., 2020), this study therefore proposes the moderating variable of board independence in the relationship between the attributes of the audit committee and the financial reporting quality. Even though the concept of board independence is theoretically argued to promote oversight and improve the quality of financial reporting (Phuong & Hung, 2020; Shatima et al., 2020), there are still underlying risks that the independence of the board could be superficial due to long tenure or close relationship with management (Bencomo, 2021). Therefore, by examining the attributes of the audit committee, including the oft-neglected attribute of the audit committee shareholding of financial services companies in Nigeria, this study hopes to improve the comprehensive understanding of the mechanisms of governance that improve the quality of financial reporting and inform the necessary policy and regulatory reforms to promote economic development and growth.

Literature review

This section reviews the theoretical and empirical research supporting the connection between financial reporting quality, board independence, and audit committee attributes.

Agency Theory

The concept of separation of ownership and management was also explored by agency theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). The theory proposed that managers, being entrusted with other people's resources, may not be as careful and responsible as owners of these resources. This could cause wastage and lack of proper management of the company. Jensen and Meckling argued that unless proper mechanisms of corporate governance were put in place, managers would always act in their own interests and not in the interests of shareholders. The relationship between shareholders and managers was viewed as that of principal and agent. The efficiency of board management was also emphasized. This was done in order to address this issue. For example, subcommittees of boards play an important role in enhancing efficiency (Kibiya et al., 2016). In addition, Heirany et al. (2013) established that the existence of AC's experience has an influence on manipulation for business or personal gains.

According to agency theory, the audit committee's main responsibility is to oversee the financial reporting and disclosure process to ensure that the firm's managers act in the best interests of the firm's shareholders. However, in order to fulfill this responsibility successfully, the audit committee should work hand-in-hand with the entire setting in which it operates. One of the integral parts of this setting includes the presence of independent directors who can act impartially to oversee the operations of the firm and assist the audit committee in fulfilling its responsibility. According to agency theory, autonomy helps decision-makers make impartial and precise decisions without any pressure to recognize and freely admit their mistakes. Al-Qublan et al. (2020) suggested that active participation of audit committee members in productive meetings helps improve financial reporting quality, which aligns with agency theory. In the same context, Medina (2022) argued that director stock ownership helps align directors' interests with those of the firm's shareholders, thus improving corporate governance by reducing conflicts of interests due to the separation of ownership and control. Board independence act as a complementary governance mechanism that strengthen the ability of audit committee to limit managerial opportunism and enhance the credibility of financial reporting. From agency point view, a board with large independent directors is more likely to support transparent disclosure practices, demand accountability and provide enabling environment for audit committee to effectively discharge its duties. This complementary relationship implies that audit committee desire to promote FRQ may be enhance when board independence is high, due to the fact that independent directors reinforce monitoring intensify and reduce the likelihood of collusion between management and internal control mechanism.

In accordance with the complementary governance hypothesis, which argued that one mechanism can enhance the effectiveness of another when both aim to reduce agency cost (Kausel & Slaughter, 2011), this propose that both effective audit committee and board independence strengthen the quality of financial reporting. Thus, board independence and audit committee function as mutually reinforcing monitoring mechanism: an effective and independent board empowers the audit committee to demand greater accountability from management, thus minimizing information asymmetry and enhance credibility of financial reporting.

Empirical Review

Audit Committee Independence and Financial Reporting Quality

Akanbi et al. (2022) investigated the impact of AC characteristics on the FRQ of selected Nigerian listed consumer goods companies. In order to measure FRQ, the study used relevance with regard to financial reports based on the interval between the accounting years the report was signed by the external auditor. From 2008 to 2019, sample data from 15 listed consumer goods companies was considered from the NSE. The study used an ex post facto research approach, and correlation analysis was employed to assess how audit committee characteristics proxied by AC independence affected the FRQ. The results indicate an insignificant positive correlation between FRQ and AC independence.

Ogunsola (2024) investigated the relationship between audit committee characteristics and earnings management in deposit money banks in Nigeria. In this study, an ex-post facto research design was used. The population of the study comprised twenty-four (24) deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group as of December 31, 2022. Due to data availability constraints, nine deposit money banks were purposively selected. Annual reports were used as the source of data, covering the period 2015-2022. The results indicated that audit committee independence positively and significantly influenced earnings management. This implies that there is a negative relationship between audit committee independence and FRQ. Conversely, audit committee financial expertise exhibited a negative and significant influence on earnings management. This implies that there is a positive relationship between audit committee financial expertise and FRQ. In contrast, audit committee size exhibited a positive influence but failed to achieve statistical significance.

Audit Committee Financial Expertise and Financial Reporting Quality

Hassan et al. (2020) the study investigated the moderating effect of audit quality on the relationship between audit committee attributes and financial reporting quality of trading companies quoted on the Bursa Malaysia and published their account from 2013 to 2018. A sample of 814 companies was selected after filtering firms with the required data. The study adopted multiple regression models. Audit quality was proxied as 1 if big four were the auditor, otherwise

The findings show that corporate governance mechanisms such as financial accounting experts as one of the proxies of audit committee attributes show a significant negative effect on financial reporting quality. In addition, the results show that audit quality Big 4 moderates the effect of audit committee financial accounting experts on financial reporting quality.

In addition to this, Salah (2021) specifically aims to examine the impact of attributes of audit committees, the quality of external auditors, and the quality of financial disclosure on quoted companies of the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries. The researcher used a sample of 115 companies over the period of 2017-2019, resulting in analyzing a total of 345 firm-year observations. The researcher used a qualitative method by applying a checklist based on the guidelines of Beest et al. (2009), with some modifications based on the amendments of the IASB conceptual framework issued in 2018. The findings of the study showed that the level of FRQ on the sample of the study averaged at 63%. The minimum and maximum values were recorded at 40% and 86%, respectively. The findings of the study clearly indicated that FRQ had a significant impact on the four attributes of ACs and the quality of outside auditors. It clearly indicates that FRQ will be influenced by ACs having a bigger size and employing high-quality auditors. Furthermore, Sitienei (2022) examines the impact of audit committee attributes on Changes in the FRQ of Manufacturing Companies in Kenya. A sample of publicly quoted firms based on 2010-2018 data was studied. A quantitative research design was adopted by the study. Population of the study was made up of nine firms listed under the manufacturing and allied sectors of the main investment market segment at the Kenya stock exchange. The research period covered 8 years, from 2010 to 2018. The study collected data via secondary methods. The findings revealed that the expertise of the committee has an insignificant positive effect on the FRQ.

Audit Committee Size and Financial Reporting Quality

In addition, Udisifan and Akeem (2019) looked into the impact of attributes of AC on the quality of financial reporting of selected quoted firms on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE), with the study period ranging from 2009 to 2018. The researcher used a sample of three conglomerate companies and nine oil and gas companies based on the census sampling technique. FRQ was proxied by Modified Jones model of discretionary accruals, whereas audit committee size was proxied by Natural logarithm of number of AC members. The data used in the study were collected through secondary sources by obtaining annual reports of the sampled companies. The data were analyzed using multiple regression. The findings showed a significant negative relationship between AC size and FRQ. Furthermore, the study by Ogaluzor and Ohaka (2019) focuses on the impact of the characteristics of AC on FRQ for consumer goods manufacturing firms that are listed on the Nigerian exchange group. The study focuses on the impact of the independence of the audit committee and the size of the audit committee on the value relevance of accounting information and earnings management. The study was conducted using the annual report of 15 consumer goods manufacturing firms that are listed on the Nigerian exchange group for eleven years (2006-2016). The findings of the study show that the size of the audit committee has a significant positive impact on the accounting value relevance of earnings, while the independence of the audit committee has an insignificant negative impact on the accounting value relevance of earnings.

Audit Committee Meeting and Financial Reporting Quality

A study by Kapkiyai (2020) examined the role played by the effectiveness of the audit committee in controlling earnings management by firms that are listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange. The researcher used panel data from audited financial reports from the year 2004 to 2017 using the panel regression model. The findings of the study revealed that the role of the audit committee is significant in controlling earnings management by the firms. Specifically, the independence of the audit committee was found to have a negative effect on earnings management. Alzeban, (2020) focused on the effectiveness of audit committees in improving the quality of financial reports, especially in manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the period 2018-2020. The study was intended to find out whether the presence of an audit committee, along with certain attributes, and the quality of audits could improve the quality of earnings. The effectiveness of the audit committee was measured in terms of certain attributes, such as the size of the audit committee, the number of meetings held, and the competence of members. Another factor, audit quality, was also taken into consideration in this study. By using the purposive sampling technique, the study collected 292 data points, and multiple linear regression was used for hypothesis testing. The results showed that the size of the audit committee and audit quality were significant factors in improving the quality of earnings, while the number of meetings held and the competence of members were not significant factors in this regard.

Audit Committee Shareholding and Financial Reporting Quality

Kibiya et al. (2016) examine the effect of audit committee attribute on FRQ. The study analyzed data from 101 listed companies over five years (2010–2014). Discretionary accruals based on the McNichols (2002) model were employed to evaluate financial reporting quality as the dependent variable, while share held by the audit committee was represented by the ratio of equity held by the committee. Multivariate regression analysis was employed to evaluate the relationships between the variables. The study discovered that committee stock ownership has a significant positive impact on FRQ. Similarly, Dakhllalh et al., (2020) explore the effect of the audit committee on firm financial performance (Tobin's Q) among Jordanian companies covering the period 2009–2017. Sample of 180 quoted firms on the Amman Stock Exchange was considered. The study proxied audit committee shareholding as one of the dimensions of AC attributes was proxy as the proportion of the company stock that audit committee members possess relative to the total number of shares. The study used secondary data obtained from the financial statements of sampled firms and multiple regression was used to analyse the data. The findings show that the AC shareholding has a significant negative effect on financial performance as proxied by Tobin's Q. This suggests that audit committee shareholding has a significant negative effect on financial reporting quality.

Board Independence and Financial Reporting Quality

Kantudu and Samaila (2015) examined the effect of monitoring characteristics on the financial reporting quality of Nigerian-listed oil marketing firms. The quality of financial reporting was assessed based on the qualitative characteristics of annual reports. The study used data obtained from the financial statements of the selected oil marketing firms over twelve years, from 2000 to 2011. Multiple regression was used to analyse data collected with the aid of Stata version 12.0. The results unveiled that separation of power, managerial shareholdings, independent directors, and independent audit committees all significantly influence the FRQ. Furthermore, Phuong and Hung (2020), the study investigated the relationship between board of directors and FRQ among Vietnam listed companies. The study uses multiple regression, data was collected from 2010 - 2018, with 2162 observations. The result unveiled that board independence, board size, and board chairperson cum CEO have a positive effect on the quality of financial reporting while board meeting frequency has a negative impact on the quality of financial reporting.

METHODOLOGY

In order to assess the correlations between the variables of interest, the study employed the panel regression techniques and the longitudinal methodology of research. The sample of the study, which covers the six-year period from 2019 to 2024, was made up of eight (8) randomly selected firms from the total population of thirty-eight (38) listed financial service firms in Nigeria. Abbey Mortgage Bank Plc, Access Bank Plc, African Alliance Insurance Plc, Aiico Insurance Plc, Axaman Standard Insurance Plc, Consolidated Hallmark Holding Plc, First Bank Holding Plc, and First City Monument Bank Plc are the firms included in the sample of the study, cutting across all the sub-sector of the financial services firms. The analysis of the secondary data was done using the statistical software Stata version 15 with the aim of producing the estimates of the analysis.

Table 1. Summary of Variable Measurement

S/N	Variable	Acronyms	Type of Variable	Measurement	Source
1.	Financial Reporting Quality	FRQ	Dependent	Discretionary Accrual Measured by the absolute value of residual	Kothari et al. (2005); Sitienei, (2022)
2.	AC Independence	ACI	Independent	Ratio of the number of independent non-executive directors on audit committee to the total number of audit committee	Hassan et al., (2020); Al-Qublani et al. (2020)
3.	AC Financial Expertise	ACFE	Independent	Ratio of AC members with financial expertise to the total number of audit committee	Agyei-Mensah, (2022); Sitienei (2022)
4.	AC Size	ACS	Independent	Total number of AC members on the board	Hassan et al., (2020); Buallay & Al-Ajmi, (2020); Galal et al. (2022)
5.	AC Meeting	ACM	Independent	Number of meetings held by audit committee during the year	Buallay & Al-Ajmi, (2020); Okechukwu et al. (2022)
6.	AC Shareholding	ACSH	Independent	Percentage of shares held by AC relative to the total No. of share	Kibiya et al. 2016); Rashid et al. (2024)
7.	Board Independence	BI	Moderator	Percentage of independent directors on the board	Phuong and Hung (2020)
8.	Firm Size	FSZ	Control	Natural log of total assets	Islam et al., (2023)
7.	Firm Age	AGE	Control	Number of years from incorporation	Shehu and Jamil, (2019)

Model Specification

$$FRQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ACI_{it} + \beta_2 ACE_{it} + \beta_3 ACS_{it} + \beta_4 ACM_{it} + \beta_5 ACSH_{it} + \beta_6 FSZ_{it} + \beta_7 AGE_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

$$FRQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ACI * BI_{it} + \beta_2 ACE * BI_{it} + \beta_3 ACS * BI_{it} + \beta_4 ACM * BI_{it} + \beta_5 ACSH * BI_{it} + \beta_6 FSZ_{it} + \beta_7 AGE_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where;

- FRQ = Financial Reporting Quality
- β_0 = is the regression coefficient
- ACI = Audit Committee Independence
- ACE = Audit Committee Financial Expertise
- ACS = Audit Committee Size
- ACM = Audit Committee Meetings
- ACSH = Audit Committee Shareholding
- BI = Board Independence
- FSZ = Firm Size
- AGE = Firm Age
- ϵ = error term

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results and discusses the key findings.

Table 2 descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.	Skewness	Kurtosis
FRQ	0.1043	0.1181	0.0022	0.5171	1.9966	6.5311
ACI	0.1458	0.1003	0.0000	0.4000	-0.0861	3.0980
ACFE	0.2215	0.1359	0.0000	0.5000	0.2396	2.6685
ACS	5.3750	0.4892	5	6	0.5164	1.2667
ACM	4.1458	0.9891	2	7	0.7719	4.8327
ACSH	0.0892	0.1418	0.0000	0.4217	1.2096	2.8109
BI	0.1865	0.1098	0	0.5455	1.5010	5.6864
FSZ	11.2649	1.0253	9.7932	13.4422	0.5840	2.1887
AGE	50.7500	31.2359	28	130	1.7913	4.8509

Source: researcher analysis 2025

The descriptive statistics of the variables in the study, such as the mean, SD, minimum, maximum, skewness, and kurtosis of the variables, are presented in Table 2. The Nigerian financial service sector companies that are the subject of the study have an average score of 0.1043 in terms of Financial Reporting Quality (FRQ) proxied by discretionary accruals and therefore manage their earnings at an average level of 10.45%. The relatively low standard deviation of 0.1181 also suggests that the values of the Financial Reporting Quality are narrowly distributed between 0.0022 and 0.5171. Regarding Audit Committee Independence (ACI) About, the proportion of the audit committee members that are independent directors is 14.58%. While some companies have as high as 40% independent members, others have no independent members at all. Audit Committee Financial experience (ACFE) with a mean of 0.2215 implies that the proportion of the audit committee members with financial experience is about 22.15%. Audit Committee Size (ACS) averages five members as required by the regulations with minimum variation. Audit Committee Meeting averages just above four meetings with significant variation. Audit Committee Shareholding (ACSH) averages at 8.92% with moderate variation.

The moderating variable, board independence, has an average of 0.1865. This implies that independent directors form 18.65% of the board. However, there is significant variation across firms. The results for the control variables indicate that the firms and their age vary fairly across the board, given that their average age is 50.75 years. The variables are normally distributed and suitable for further inferential analysis given that their values for skewness and kurtosis are within acceptable limits.

Table 3. Result of Pearson Correlation (N = 48)

Variable	FRQ	ACI	ACFE	ACS	ACM	ACSH	BI	FZS	AGE
FRQ	1.0000								
ACI	0.1249	1.0000							
ACFE	0.0037	-0.1850	1.0000						
ACS	0.0781	-0.1843	0.2814	1.0000					
ACM	0.5712*	-0.0974	-0.1400	-0.0275	1.0000				
ACSH	0.6292*	-0.2468	0.3915*	0.1467	0.3692*	1.0000			
BI	0.0018	0.5281*	0.0335	0.0491	-0.1012	-0.2543	1.0000		
FSZ	-0.3243*	0.2821	0.0021	-0.0748	-0.4049*	-0.1996	0.2442	1.0000	
AGE	-0.2057	0.5162*	0.1995	0.0411	-0.1730	-0.4001*	0.6801*		1.0000
								0.0299	

Source: researcher analysis 2025

The extent and nature of the linear relationships between two variables are examined by correlation analysis (Pallant, 2005). In this study, as shown in Table 3, Pearson correlation analysis was employed to establish the nature of the relationships between the variables of the study. The correlation coefficient, denoted by r , measures the extent of the relationships. In the case of Financial Reporting Quality (FRQ), as shown in Table 2, Board Independence (BI), Audit Committee Independence (ACI), Audit Committee Financial Expertise (ACFE), and Audit Committee Size (ACS) were all found to have a positive though statistically insignificant correlation with FRQ. However, a negative and statistically significant correlation with FRQ was found for Audit Committee Shareholding (ACSH), Audit Committee Meeting (ACM), while Firm Age (AGE) had a negative though statistically insignificant correlation with FRQ. Firm Size (FSZ), on the other hand, had a strong negative correlation with FRQ.

Table 4. VIF and Tolerance Values

Variables	VIF	1/VIF
ACI	1.94	0.51
ACFE	2.07	0.48
ACS	1.14	0.88
ACM	1.52	0.66
ACSH	2.27	0.44
BI	2.27	0.44
FSZ	1.53	0.66
AGE	3.50	0.29
Mean VIF	2.03	

High correlation exists between independent variables, especially when the correlation coefficient is at or above 0.9. This leads to multicollinearity. In this study, it is clear that no correlation exists between any of the independent variables, as all are at low correlation levels according to the correlation matrix. This proves that multicollinearity does not exist in this data set, as indicated by the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and tolerance methods used in checking for multicollinearity. This proves that multicollinearity does not exist in the data set, as indicated by the tolerance value ranging from 0.29 to 0.88 and the VIF value ranging from 1.14 to 3.50.

Table 5. Heteroskedasticity Test

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity	
Chi2	= 10.85
Prob > Chi2	= 0.0010

Source: Researcher Computation (2025)

Homoscedasticity assumes that the variance of regression residuals should be constant across all values of independent variables in multivariate analysis. The violation of this assumption leads to heteroscedasticity, which may arise due to non-normality, measurement errors, and changes in variables, thus leading to varying error terms. This may impair the reliability of the results if heteroscedasticity is not controlled, although it does not render the results invalid. The Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test indicated significant heteroscedasticity for the FRQ model in this study ($p = 0.001$), indicating a wide range of variation in the residuals. Panel Corrected Standard Errors (PCSEs) were used to deal with heteroscedasticity, as recommended by literature, ensuring the reliability of the results without making any changes to the model selection process.

Table 6. regression results of model 1 (direct relationship)

Variable	Coef.	T	p>t
Constant	0.1004	0.56	0.577
Independent:			
ACI	0.4516	3.32	0.001***
ACFE	-0.0649	-0.69	0.490
ACS	0.0195	0.84	0.403
ACM	0.0332	2.15	0.032**
ACSH	0.4474	3.2	0.001***
Moderator:			
BI	0.2113	2.13	0.034**
Control:			
FSZ	-0.0285	-2.77	0.006***
AGE	-0.0010	-1.84	0.066
Observations		48	
No. of groups		8	
R ²		0.6835	
Wald chi2 (8)		125.05	
Prob>chi2		0.0000	

Notes: ***, **, and * represent significant at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels respectively

Table 6 shows the direct relationship regression results. Approximately 68.35% of the FRQ ($R^2 = 0.6835$) variation in Nigerian listed financial services firms is explained by the model. An excellent fit and dependability of the estimates are indicated by the statistical significance of the entire model (wald $\chi^2(8) = 125.05$, $p < 0.01$). Furthermore, the findings indicated that the characteristics of the audit committee had an impact on FRQ as measured by discretionary accruals. At the 1% level, Audit Committee Independence (ACI) has an excellent positive correlation with discretionary accruals, indicating that an increase in independence is associated with higher earnings management, hence lower FRQ. Audit Committee Size (ACS) and Audit Committee Financial Expertise (ACFE) have no significant impact on FRQ, indicating that these characteristics have no impact on earnings management. At the 5% level, the results on audit committee meetings (ACM) indicate a significant positive effect, implying that more frequent audit committee meetings are associated with greater discretionary accruals and lower FRQ. On the other hand, at the 1 percent level, there is a significant positive effect on Audit Committee Shareholding (ACSH), implying that with greater shareholding, discretionary accruals are greater. Finally, at the 5 percent level, there is a strong positive correlation between Board Independence (BI) and discretionary accruals, implying that greater independence is associated with more earnings management rather than better financial reporting.

Table 7. regression results of model 2 (indirect relationship)

Variable	Coef.	T	p>t
Constant	0.0507	0.2	0.845
Independent:			
ACI_BI	-2.2852	-4.04	0.000***
ACFE_BI	-0.9296	-1.85	0.065
ACS_BI	-0.0195	-0.13	0.898
ACM_BI	-0.1430	-0.73	0.467
ACSH_BI	3.4304	2.17	0.030
Observations		48	
No. of groups		8	
R ²		0.7848	
Wald chi2 (13)		136.98	
Prob>chi2		0.0000	

Notes: ***, **, and * represent significant at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels respectively

Table 7 regression analysis reveals that the association between audit committee independence and Financial Reporting Quality (FRQ) is moderated by board independence. Because the indirect link demonstrates a significant negative impact on earnings management, which results in a significant positive effect on FRQ, whereas the direct relationship demonstrates a significant positive impact on earnings management, which results in a significant negative effect on FRQ. However, Table 5 finding indicates that the association between audit committee financial expertise and financial reporting quality is not moderated by board independence. Regarding audit committee size, Table 7 findings indicate that the association between audit committee size and financial reporting quality (FRQ) is moderated by board independence. Because the indirect relationship indicates that audit committee size has an insignificant negative effect on earnings management, which means an insignificant positive effect on FRQ, whereas the direct relationship indicates that audit committee size has an insignificant positive effect on earnings management, which means an insignificant negative effect on FRQ.

In a similar vein, Table 7 audit committee meeting results indicate that the association between audit committee meetings and financial reporting quality (FRQ) is moderated by board independence. Because the indirect relationship indicates that audit committee meetings have an insignificant negative impact on earnings management and an insignificant positive impact on FRQ, whereas the direct relationship indicates that audit committee meetings have a significant positive impact on earnings management and a significant negative impact on FRQ. Finally, Table 5 findings regarding audit committee shareholding demonstrate that the relationship between audit committee shareholding and financial reporting quality (FRQ) is not moderated by board independence.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Given the direct relationship, the findings indicate that audit committee independence significantly reduces FRQ, but financial expertise was found to have no significant positive effect. Audit committee meetings had a significant negative effect on FRQ, but audit committee size was found to have no significant negative effect on FRQ. This could indicate that frequent meetings may actually be symbolic in nature. Furthermore, the shareholding of the audit committee was found to reduce FRQ significantly, which could indicate that equity holding leads to compromised independence and ultimately leads to conflicts of interest. These findings indicate that although governance mechanisms are in place, the realities of the institutional context of the Nigerian environment affect the efficacy of the same mechanisms. The moderating role of independence on the board showed mixed results. Consistent with agency theory, independence had a significant impact on the role of audit committee independence on FRQ, though it had no significant impact on the roles of size and financial expertise. The negative impact of audit committee meetings was influenced by board independence, though this impact was found to be insignificant. Furthermore, the negative impact of audit committee ownership could not be negated by independence, thus showing the difficulties involved in managing ownership conflicts. The findings of the study thus emphasize the importance of functional enforcement and institutional effectiveness in ensuring that audit committees and boards function efficiently in Nigeria, as opposed to relying on structural characteristics to improve reporting quality.

The study thus makes several recommendations to improve the functional efficacy of audit committees and boards to transcend mere symbolic compliance. It thus becomes imperative for regulatory bodies to emphasize the quality of audit committee meetings rather than their frequency, limit audit committee shareholding to reduce conflicts of interest, and review independence standards to make them truly independent. It also becomes important to improve the practical and industry-specific financial knowledge of audit committee members through continuous professional development. Moreover, the effectiveness of independent directors in oversight is subject to the support provided. In other words, the effectiveness of independent directors in oversight is subject to enforcement and institutional support. Therefore, in order to improve financial reporting quality in Nigeria, it is important that there are proper governance structures in place, in addition to proper institutions and culture of accountability in financial services firms.

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